

Interactions of morphine and codeine with benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acids

Dilip Kumar Kuila^a and S. C. Lahiri^{b*}

^aCentral Forensic Science Laboratory, 30, Gorachand Road, Kolkata-700 014, India

E-mail : kuiladk@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Kalyani University, Kalyani-741 235, India

E-mail : sujitclahiri@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 3 November 2003, revised 10 April 2004, accepted 17 May 2004

Interactions of morphine and codeine with benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acids in methanol have been investigated spectrophotometrically. Morphine and codeine form fairly stable and similar complexes with the ligands. The complexes formed are assumed to be due to Van der Waals type of co-operative effects of different forces together with the possibility of H-bonding. The aromatic compounds are accommodated to the flat surface or cavity part of piperidine ring of morphine and codeine.

Different aspects of molecular interactions like charge transfer (CT) or electron donor-acceptor reactions, H-bonding etc. were widely studied and reported^{1,2}. Nevertheless, real explanation for the weak interactions is still not known with certainty. These aspects demand further studies and exploration. Naturally a systematic study of these complexes is to be pursued.

In recent years, a number of studies on molecular or CT complexes were made. Some of these are; complexes between phenothiazine and unsaturated acid anhydrides³, anthraquinone anticancer drugs with suitable donors⁴, complexes between *o*-chloranil and phenols and polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons^{5,6}, complexes between (60 and 70) fullerenes with methylated pyridines and methyl benzenes^{7,8}, pyrazole derivatives with π -electron acceptors⁹.

These studies stimulated us to undertake similar studies with some known drugs like morphine and codeine. It is known that drug-receptor interactions involve a large number of competitive weak interactions like CT interaction, H-bonding, Van der Waals interactions etc.

Morphine and codeine are the main constituents of opium and are structurally related narcotic analgesics obtainable from plant source (Poppy plant, *Papaver Somniferum*)^{10,11}. They have phenanthrene type of structure. Morphine, due to its peculiar structure (Fig. 1a,c) has been subject to various structural modifications to give compounds of varied analgesic and other medicinal activities¹⁰⁻¹². The relationship between chemical structure

Fig. 1. (a) Structure of morphine, (b) structure of codeine and (c) diagram of the surface of the analgesic receptor site with the corresponding lower surface of the drug molecule (morphine).

and analgesic action of morphine and codeine and some aspects of drug-receptor interactions were widely studied¹³⁻¹⁵. Drugs form different types of complexes like molecular complexes, charge transfer (CT), electron donor-

acceptor, H-bonding etc. with various ligands.

Due to their peculiar structure, morphine and codeine also have the capability of forming complexes with different molecules and receptors.

Higuchi and co-workers¹⁶ studied the complex formation between caffeine and a large number of compounds of varied nature including benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acids.

It will be interesting to study similar complexes between morphine and codeine with benzoic acid (BA), *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid (pHBA), *p*-amino benzoic acid (pABA) and *m*-nitro benzoic acid (mNBA). The results of our investigations are presented in this communication.

Results

Assuming 1 : 1 complex formation between the drugs (D) (acting as donors) and the ligands (A) (acting as acceptors), the association constant for the reaction.

can be written as

$$K_{DA} = \frac{[DA]}{[D][A]} \cdot \frac{\gamma_{DA}}{\gamma_D \cdot \gamma_A} \approx \frac{x}{(C_1 - x)(C_2 - x)} \quad (2)$$

In view of non-electrolytic nature of the reactants and complexes and at low concentrations $\gamma_{DA}/\gamma_D \cdot \gamma_A$ (γ represents activity coefficients of the respective species) can be regarded to be unity. C_1 and C_2 represents the initial concentrations of D and A respectively, x represent the equilibrium concentration of the complex DA.

The usual procedure of determining K_{DA} using Benesi-Hildebrand¹⁷ or Scott¹⁸ equation have been avoided and an interactive procedure¹⁹⁻²³ using the equation

$$\frac{C_1}{(d - d_1 - d_2)} = \frac{1}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)l} + \frac{1}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)(C_2 - x)l} \cdot \frac{1}{K_{DA}} \quad (3)$$

(where $l = 1 \text{ cm}$)

were used for the determination of association constants.

$$\text{Here, } d_1 = \epsilon_1 C_1 l \quad (4)$$

$$d_2 = \epsilon_2 C_2 l \quad (5)$$

$$d = \epsilon x l + \epsilon_1 (C_1 - x)l + \epsilon_2 (C_2 - x)l \quad (6)$$

All the components and the complexes absorb strongly in the region of interest i.e. UV region

Thus,

$$x = \frac{d - d_1 - d_2}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)} \quad (7)$$

x was assumed to be zero initially, and from the plot of $C_1/(d - d_1 - d_2)$ against $1/C_2$, an approximate values of $1/(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)$ and x were determined. The value of x was utilized to get a refined value of x from the plot of $C_1/(d - d_1 - d_2)$ against $1/(C_2 - x)$.

The iteration was repeated till constant values of $1/(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)$ and K_{DA} were obtained. The molar absorptivities ϵ of the complexes and the equilibrium constants K_{DA} at 298 K are recorded in Table 1. ΔG^0 values were calculated from the relation

$$\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K_{DA} \quad (8)$$

Discussion

Structure of morphine and codeine are presented in Fig 1a and 1b.

Both have similar structure but in codeine, phenolic-OH group is alkylated. This does not change the wavelength of maximum absorption of codeine (286 nm). The maxima

Table 1. λ_{\max} , Equilibrium constant (K), extinction coefficient (ϵ) and free energy (ΔG^0), values for complexes between drugs (morphine and codeine) and different acceptors at 298 K in methanol

Nature of drug	λ_{\max} of drug (nm)	Acceptors	λ_{\max} of acceptors (nm)	λ_{\max} of complexes (nm)	$K_{DA} \times 10^4$ ($\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) at 25°	ϵ ($\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$\log K_{DA}$	$-\Delta G$ (kJ mol^{-1})
Morphine	286	BA	227, 272	280	13.0	2368	5.11	29.10
		<i>p</i> -HBA	250.5	247	1.95	18131	4.29	24.47
		<i>p</i> -ABA	270	280	0.20	16403	3.3	18.83
		<i>m</i> -NBA	261	262	51.7	10279	5.71	32.6
Codeine	286	BA	227, 272	280	47.4	2118	5.67	32.38
		<i>p</i> -HBA	250.5	247	30.0	14492	5.47	31.25
		<i>p</i> -ABA	270	280	4.7	18040	4.67	26.65
		<i>m</i> -NBA	261	262	747.0	14594	6.87	39.21

are likely to be due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition where $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition arising from tertiary N-atom present in the molecules is superimposed. The maxima of benzoic acids are due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions where substituents show considerable blue shift with respect to BA.

There are visible changes in the spectra when the morphine or codeine react with the benzoic acids and changes in o.d. values indicate complex formation. However, the complexes and the components absorb in the same region increasing the complexities of determination of association constants. There is blue shifts with respect to morphine or codeine but red shift (except pHBA) with respect to benzoic acids.

It is to be noted that morphine (analgesic activity 100), codeine (phenolic-OH is replaced by -OCH₃ group, analgesic activity 15), thebaine (both phenolic and alcoholic-OH groups are replaced by -OCH₃ groups, analgesic activity 0) have similar spectra and absorption maxima at 286 nm though they are energetically different¹⁰. All are highly stable and the complexes studied here have similar absorption maxima indicating that the complexes are similar in nature. Seal and coworkers^{5,6} also observed no new peak on mixing phenols with *o*-chloranil but the absorption is intensified.

Most of the determinations of the association constants of weak complexes were done by Benesi-Hildebrand equation¹⁷. The conditions stipulated are :

- (i) only the complex should absorb in the region of measurement. This may be true in certain cases but in most of the cases one of the components (even both) absorbs,
- (ii) the concentration of one of the components usually D (donor) should be much higher (100 to 1000 times) than that of A i.e. $D \gg A$.

Under these conditions, we have

$$K_{\Gamma A} = \frac{[DA]}{[(A) - (DA)][D]} = \frac{[x]}{(C_1 - x)C_2} \quad (9)$$

low values of K_{DA} are expected and it is apparent from the values given in the literature^{1,2}. But if D, A and DA absorb in the same region, Benesi-Hildebrand equation (B-H equation) fails. The eq. (3) reduces to

$$\frac{C_1}{d} = \frac{1}{\epsilon} + \frac{1}{\epsilon K_{DA}} \cdot \frac{1}{C_2} \quad (10)$$

(if $D \gg A$ or $C_2 \gg C_1$)

Plots of C_1/d against $1/C_2$ are made to get K_{DA} (B-H).

However, x is never proportional to C_2 and changes in $(C_1 - x)$ is only marginal, i.e. the B-H equation (10) cannot give accurate values of K_{DA} . The use of B-H equation is not applicable to strong complexes but the eq. (3) is applicable in case of strong and weak complexes alike.

According to Foster²⁴ "more weight should be given to association constant values obtained from optical data under the condition $[D]_0 = [A]_0$ and to values derived from NMR chemical shift data, rather than optical density measurements of the charge transfer band on solutions in which one solute species is present in large excess". In addition to the possibilities of presence of termolecular and isomeric complexes, specific solvation etc.; "the experimental determination of the optical absorption due to complex may be made difficult by the absorption of the component molecules themselves". This is particularly true "for weak complexes where only a small fraction of either component is complexed"^{25,26}. Here B-H equation fails. Foster²⁴ also compiled a table consisting of anomalous K_{DA} values.

Thus, it is desirable to have K_{DA} values when the concentrations of the constituents are in stoichiometric proportions i.e.

$$K_{DA} = \frac{[DA]}{[(A) - (DA)][(D) - (DA)]} = \frac{x}{(C_1 - x)(C_2 - x)} \quad (11)$$

K_{DA} values should be high.

In our study, all the components absorb in the region of interest and the method of iteration used by us are more appropriate.

Moreover, in any type of complexes, most accurate values of the equilibrium constants (here association constants) are obtained when the reactants are in the stoichiometric ratios.

The high K_{DA} values suggest strong complex formation.

Due to peculiar structure, morphine and codeine can interact with compounds having variable structures with varied interactions. Extensive studies on drug-receptor interactions have been made with morphine¹⁰⁻¹⁴.

In the present study, we are not interested in drug-receptor (D-R) interactions but we want to explore the possibilities of different types of interactions of morphine and codeine with different ligands (or acceptors) and try to understand the forces responsible for drug-receptor interactions. However, it is difficult as the spectral changes may

be due to dispersion interactions, dipole-induced dipole, dipole-dipole and other short-range interactions like CT and H-bonding²⁷.

Morphine and codeine have a rigid T-shaped structure with two broad water repelling surfaces at right angles to each other, a hydroxyl group (OH) capable of hydrogen bonding and a positively charged nitrogen atom that can form an ionic bond^{10,11,28}.

They have

- (i) a flat structure that allows a linkage with the aromatic ring of the drug through Van der Waals type forces,
- (ii) an anionic site able to associate with the positively charged basic centers of the drugs,
- (iii) a suitably oriented cavity to accommodate the -CH₂-CH₂- portion (relative to C₁₅-C₁₆) projecting from the piperidine that lies in front of the plane containing the aromatic ring and the basic center.

Beckett and Casy^{10,11,14} proposed a complementary receptor site in which action molecules can be adopted (Fig. 1c). The possibility of more than one type of D-R complexation with different modes of interactions has been suggested^{10,11,15} and is apparent from Fig. 1c. However, stereo specificity is not of importance^{10,11,15}.

From the discussion it is apparent that the formation of strong irreversible co-valent complexes or strong ionic complexes is not possible. But different types of weak interactions play significant role in the formation of stable complexes and are particularly important in understanding DR interactions.

All the compounds have a skeleton of benzene ring capable of forming CT and hydrogen bonding complexes. They have in general flat planar structures modified by the substituents like -OH, -NO₂, -NH₂ and have high dipole moments increasing the possibility of Van der Waals type forces like dipole-dipole and dispersion interactions.

It has been found that both morphine and codeine form complexes with benzoic acids. The complexes are similar in nature and the stabilities of the complexes are similar. The changes in stability arises from the substitutional effects. The substitution of phenolic OH group (morphine) by OCH₃ group (codeine) increases the stability of the complexes. The stability of the complexes is in the order : mNBA > BA > pHBA > pABA.

The greater stability constant of mNBA is due to its greater dipole moment and dispersion interactions.

The introduction of substituents like -COOH, -NO₂, -OH, -NH₂ groups (in benzene ring) change the planar structure of benzene ring and they become to some extent buckled and non-planar. They are accommodated in cavity for part of piperidine ring of morphine and codeine. Van der Waals forces together with H-bonding interaction are expected to play vital role in the formation of complexes though CT forces may have contributions. The dimension of the benzoic acid molecules is important. The accommodation of pABA (~6.7 Å) and pHBA (~6.0 Å) causes greater strain. The greater the size of the acids, the lesser is the stability as observed from *K*_{DA} values.

The contribution due to CT interaction is probably small. However, the possibility of formation of salts with benzoic acids with the mono-acidic base cannot also be ruled out. The nature of the weak interactions and identification of their contributions separately are almost impossible to ascertain. It is to be noted that the complexes between quinones and benzene may be due to dipolar forces²⁹ or due to

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of (a) benzoic acid, (b) morphine and (c) complex of benzoic acid + morphine.

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of (a) codeine, (b) *p*-hydroxy-benzoic acid and (c) complex of *p*-hydroxy-benzoic acid + codeine.

$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ CT complexes³⁰. Similarly, the prototype charge transfer complex between benzene and iodine is actually a complex held together by electrostatic, polarization and dispersion energies in the ground state³¹.

Experimental

Purification of drugs : Morphine (from Opium Factory, Gazipur, U.P.) was dissolved in methanol and crystallized twice. Codeine (from Opium Factory, Gazipur, U.P.) was dissolved in ethanol and crystallized twice. Benzoic acid (G.R., E. Merck) was purified by sublimation in a steam bath. *p*-Amino benzoic acid (G.R., E. Merck) was purified by crystallization from dilute ethanol. *p*-Hydroxy benzoic acid (G.R., E. Merck) was taken as such. *m*-Nitrobenzoic acid (G.R., E. Merck) was purified by crystallization from water.

Purity of the samples was checked by melting point determination.

Fig. 4. Variation of absorbance with wavelength (nm) of codeine + pHBA in methanol at different concentrations : (a) 1.0×10^{-5} (M), (b) 1.5×10^{-5} (M), (c) 2.0×10^{-5} (M), (d) 2.5×10^{-5} (M), (e) 3.0×10^{-5} (M), (f) 3.5×10^{-5} (M), (g) 4.0×10^{-5} (M).

Methanol (Spectroscopic Grade, E. Merck) was used as such.

All other chemicals and solvents used are of analytical grade.

Morphine and codeine absorb strongly in the UV region and absorption maxima at 286 nm. The ligands like BA, pHBA, pABA, mNBA absorb strongly in the UV region. Benzoic acids when mixed with morphine and codeine showed considerable shift in the absorption maxima and change in optical densities indicating complex formation. The wavelengths of absorption maxima of benzoic acids and the complexes are given in Table 1. Some typical absorption curves are presented in Figs. 2–4.

No solvent shift phenomenon were observed for drugs using solvents like methanol, chloroform, acetonitrile, benzene, heptane and carbon tetrachloride.

For determination of the association constants of the complexes, the components were mixed in different pro-

Table 2. Complex formation between codeine and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid (pHBA) in methanol and determination of equilibrium constant (*K*) at 247 nm

Concen. of codeine $C_1 \times 10^5$ (mol dm ⁻³)	Concen. of pHBA $C_2 \times 10^5$ (mol dm ⁻³)	o.d. of codeine (d_1)	o.d. of pHBA (d_2)	o.d. of complex (d)	$\frac{C_1}{d-d_1-d_2} \times 10^5$	$\frac{1}{C_2} \times 10^5$	$\frac{1}{C_2-x} \times 10^5$	From the plot of $C_1/(d-d_1-d_2)$ against $1/(C_2-x)$
1.0	1.0	0.041	0.060	0.111	100	1.00	1.55	
1.5	1.5	0.053	0.128	0.202	71.43	0.67	1.32	Intercept = 3.75×10^{-4}
2.0	2.0	0.065	0.201	0.293	74.07	0.50	0.96	
2.5	2.5	0.074	0.276	0.390	62.50	0.40	1.03	Slope = 26.15×10^{-10}
3.0	3.0	0.080	0.340	0.473	56.60	0.33	0.89	$K = 1.43 \times 10^5$
3.5	3.5	0.088	0.412	0.559	59.32	0.29	0.71	
4.0	4.0	0.093	0.476	0.661	43.47	0.25	1.36	

From the plot of $C_1/(d-d_1-d_2)$ against $1/C_2$, intercept, $1/(\epsilon-\epsilon_1-\epsilon_2) = 3.55 \times 10^{-4}$

Iteration (1) From the plot of $[C_1/(d-d_1-d_2)]$ $\times 10^5$	Iteration (2) From the plot of $[1/(C_2-x)]$ $\times 10^5$	Iteration (3) From the plot of $[C_1/(d-d_1-d_2)]$ $\times 10^5$	Iteration (4) From the plot of $[1/(C_2-x)]$ $\times 10^5$
100	1.59	1.97	2.02
71.43	1.40	1.21	1.24
74.07	1.01	-0.66	-0.62
62.50	1.13	2.44	2.82
56.60	0.98	-0.62	-0.57
59.32	0.77	-1.01	-0.90
43.47	1.81	-0.60	-0.55

Average value of $K = 30.05 \times 10^4$ and $\epsilon = 14492$.

portions. The optical densities (o.d.) of the mixtures and their components were measured at the wavelengths of the respective absorption maximum of the complexes. A representative table (Table 2) is also presented.

Spectroscopic measurements were taken at 298 K with a Shimadzu Double Beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Model UV 2550) with thermoelectrically temperature controlled cell compartment.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. M. S. Rao, Chief Forensic Scientist, Directorate of Forensic Science, New Delhi and Dr. V. K. Kashyap, Director, Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Kolkata for their keen interest and encouragement. The authors also convey their sincere thanks to staffs of chemistry and explosive divisions of CFSL, Kolkata for their assistance.

References

1. R. Foster, "Organic Charge-Transfer Complexes", Academic Press, London and New York, 1969.

2. M. A. Slifkin, "Charge-Transfer Interactions of Biomolecules", Academic Press, London, 1971.
3. H. Song, P. Huan and B. Ymg, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2003, **59**, 1509.
4. T. M. El-Gogary, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2003, **59**, 1009.
5. K. Datta, A. K. Mukherjee, M. Banerjee and B. K. Seal, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 1997, **53**, 2587.
6. B. Chakraborty, A. K. Mukherjee and B. K. Seal, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2001, **57**, 223.
7. S. Bhattacharya, S. K. Nayak, S. K. Chattopadhyay, M. Banerjee and A. K. Mukherjee, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2001, **57**, 309.
8. S. Bhattacharya, M. Banerjee and A. K. Mukherjee, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2002, **58**, 2563.
9. A. A. A. Boraie, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2002, **58**, 1895.
10. Wilson and Gisvold in R. F. Doerge (eds.), "Textbook of Organic Medicinal and Pharmaceutical Chemistry", J. B. Lippincott Company, Philadelphia, 8th. ed., 1982, pp. 608-623.
11. A. Korolkovas, "Essentials of Medicinal Chemistry", 2nd. ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1988, pp. 240-247.
12. A. Albert, "Selective Toxicity", 6th. ed., Chapman and Hall, London, pp. 516-518.

13. A. H. Beckett and A. F. Casy, *Prog. Med. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 171.
14. A. F. Casy, *Prog. Drug Res.*, 1978, **22**, 149.
15. P. S. Portoghese, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, **8**, 609; *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1978, **11**, 21.
16. A. Martin, "Physical Pharmacy", International student ed., Lippincott Williams and Wilkins, Philadelphia, 4th. ed., 2001 (reprint), pp. 265-267.
17. H. A. Benesi and J. H. Hildebrand, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **11**, 2703.
18. R. L. Scott, *Recl. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas, Belg.*, 1956, **75**, 787.
19. S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 715.
20. K. K. Majumder and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 163; 1997, **74**, 378; 2000, **77**, 447.
21. R. Mondal (Karan) and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1998, **205**, 69.
22. R. Mondal (Karan) and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 347.
23. J. Gangopadhyay and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 2001, **215**, 37, 837.
24. R. Foster, "Organic Charge-Transfer Complexes", Academic Press, London and New York, 1969, Chap. 7.
25. J. Peters and W. B. Person, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 10.
26. W. B. Person, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 167.
27. C. N. Rao, S. Singh and V. P. Senthilnathan, *Chem. Soc. Rev. (London)*, 1976, **5**, 297.
28. S. H. Synder, *Nature (London)*, 1987, **326**, 824.
29. J. Ronayne and D. H. Williams, *Chem. Commun.*, 1966, 712; P. Laszlo and D. H. Williams, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 2799.
30. R. Foster and C. A. Fyfe, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1966, **62**, 1400.
31. M. Itanna, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 285; R. Lefevre, D. V. Redford and P. Stilas, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1968, 1297.